

THE LINGUISTIC AUTHORITATIVENESS OF *MONYALA KA PEDI* AS A PRINCIPLE OF NEGOTIATING MARRIAGE

Mojalefa Lehlohonolo Koenane and Moeketsi Letseka

University of South Africa

letsem@unisa.ac.za; koenamlj@unisa.ac.za

ABSTRACT

The article seeks to correct the common perception that bohadi is paid as a bride price. It argues that the misuse of language, significantly distorts meaning, resulting in misunderstanding of its original true meaning. The purpose of this article is to argue that the Basotho principle monyala ka pedi effectively reflects that bohadi is not paid, but given, as an expression of gratitude and as a symbol of respect for culture. We argue that African ontology becomes more prominent in bohadi negotiations. Therefore, it is unthinkable that the ancestors would be excluded when the quantum of bohadi is considered.

Keywords: Basotho, culture, negotiating marriage, *mahadi*, *ilobolo*.

INTRODUCTION

Among the Bantu speaking peoples of Southern Africa, it is standard practice for families of young men and women to negotiate *ilobola* (Nguni), or *mahadi* (Sotho) – dowry for their youngsters of mature age. All Bantu speaking groups living in southern Africa regard it as a normal practice for families of young men and women to negotiate marriage for their youngsters of mature age. The word Bantu is not used derogatory as was the case during the apartheid era. The nomenclature *Bantu* refers to all the Bantu speaking peoples of Southern Africa. The spread of the Bantu languages over the subcontinent is a comprehensively chronicled matter of history (Vansina, J., 1995; Kaphagawani, 1987). There are 600 Bantu languages recorded by linguists. Southern African Bantu speaking peoples such as the Sothos and the Ngunis are part of this large family of the Bantu speaking peoples.

Therefore, marriage among Bantu speaking groups is everybody's event, from negotiation moving forward. This indicates that marriage is an important event not only in the lives of the two families but also to the larger community. In this way, marriage is not exclusively a 'two-person' matter: it is everybody's business, in the true sense of the word. The two individuals are not isolated by marriage: on the contrary, the couple's marriage brings into reality interrelationships with others, including ancestors or the living dead (*badimo*). Bujo (1998: 94) argues:

Every person who intends to marry must know that he or she embraces the whole community. This community does not only comprise the living, but all the ancestors who founded this clan [...].

The issue of *mahadi/ilobolo* is of significant value for a number of reasons, one of which is the avoidance of the embarrassment of elopement or *chobedisano*

(Koenane, 2014: 2202). *Chobedisano* is the Sesotho expression, which means elopement. 'Elopement' refers to two young people agreeing to marry without *mahadi* negotiation. Broadly speaking, there are many reasons that could lead to elopement, some of which could be legitimate and others not.

THE ONTOLOGICAL ASPECT OF MARRIAGE

Marriage among Bantu people has an ontological aspect. In this section, we argue that the ontological aspect of negotiating *mahadi* reflects a worldview that makes African marriages unique. In the understanding of African reality, there is no distinction between the living human beings and deceased. In fact, in most African belief systems, it is the duty of survivors to maintain communication open between them and the ancestors. This suggests that the living-dead take interest in the social transactions of those left behind. Mbiti (1990) refers to the deceased as the living dead, Imafidon (2012: 3) writes:

[...] ontological account of reality is a comprehensive account of their experience of the world, of the universe informed by a theory of being or a principle of reality.

Among Bantu people, marriage is part of the self and being. Marriage is a natural phenomenon; it is an expression of life between two people. When a young man reaches maturity, the first question people ask is 'are you married?' If the answer is negative, the next question would be: 'when are you getting married?' The follow-up question is 'how many children do you have?' In a way, there is the assumption of a relationship between one's ontological being and one's becoming: 'becoming' entails marriage. As Pitsoe (2016) argues that both being and becoming are ontic and constitute an ontological journey. This 'ontological journey' begins at marriage. For Bujo (1998: 93) marriage among Africans is the 'focus of existence.'

Epistemologically, negotiating *mahadi* and giving *mahadi* means giving the woman the respect she deserves as well as giving her a status in the new family. Further, we argue that by learning a specific language, one learns a given culture. Put differently, culture is embedded in language, the two are inseparable. Having established the value of language among its users, we need to consider certain vocabulary, which distorts original meanings, whether purposely or unintentionally. Masolo (1994: 245) articulates: 'one is able to arrive at the structure of reality of a particular people beginning from their language.' Consequently, the idea of paying *ilobolo* is a good example, and a misnomer. *Bohadi* is not paid but given to the woman's family because *bohadi/ilobolo* is not a price. To a woman to whose family *bohadi* is given, this is an honour and reassures the woman that she is valuable and respected. Evidently, a person who speaks about 'paying' *ilobolo* misses the point and fails to understand the 'structure of reality' (Masolo, 1994: 245) of Basotho people as Masolo (1994: 245).

DIFFERING OPINIONS ON *MAHADI*

Opinions on *ilobolo* or *mahadi* differ from one person to the other. Some view it as a money making scam through commercialisation of their children (that is, self-enrichment), while others still regard *mahadi* negotiations as an integral part of being an African, or in this case specifically a Mosotho. Those who perceive *mahadi* negotiations as a scam call for its abolishment; but on the other hand, many still believe it to be a valuable practice that should be kept but purified of those who undermine it. Among Basotho people, *mahadi* serves as a way of cementing relationships between the two families. Rajuili (2004: 14) emphasises the importance of *mahadi* thus:

The *ilobolo* cattle or whatever item was used as legal tender functioned as a means of establishing and sealing the relationship between the couple, their respective lineages, both the living and the dead, the ancestors or the shades.

We pointed out earlier that for African people marriage is not between two people, but, like all other aspects of an African worldview, is a communal issue. In this ontological journey the idiomatic expression *monyala ka pedi* does not emphasise the monetary value of *lobola* which, as many argue, has become commercialised, but instead places emphasis on its symbolic value. *Monyala ka pedi* expresses the truth of what Bujo (1998: 93) understands as the ‘focus of existence;’ in the sense that this emphasises the right of every normal person to marriage, including poor people, so that they are not deprived of this birth-right on the basis of being economically disadvantaged. It then becomes clear that *lobola* negotiations among Basotho people and other African people were originally meant for purposes other than what they have become. Because of their hidden agendas and motives of greed, it is clear that certain people have acted unethically to the extent that the original intention of *bohadi* has been completely distorted. Nowadays, people seek to enrich themselves through *ilobolo*. Wealth among Basotho people is measured by owning livestock, particularly in the form of cattle.

According to cultural norms, marriage is understood as everybody’s natural right, which no one should be denied. Just because people are poor and cannot afford *mahadi*, should not debar them from getting married. Through their lived experiences, Basotho people have formulated idioms such as *monyala ka pedi* [...] to express this concept according to their cultural beliefs. *Monyala ka pedi* is an idiomatic expression that takes into practical consideration everybody’s wealth status to ensure that money does not determine or define marriage. This is again a wise way of regulating marriage, because the most important aspect of *monyala ka pedi* is that it emphasises the value of the relationship between two families and encourages young people to enter into marriage properly, and to respect traditional Basotho values regarding marital relationships.

Bohadi among Basotho people has two forms of moral significance; the first of which is showing respect to the family of the woman to avoid the disrespectful *vat-en-sit* (Koenane, 2014: 2206) practice, which is becoming more common as

people take marriage lightly and enter into it with hidden agendas, and ulterior motives. The second moral dimension of Basotho marriage is procreation. In Koenane (2014: 2203) *vat-en-sit* is also explained as a trial marriage where a couple live together without commitment to a permanent marital relationship. Most trial marriages do not succeed because there were no *mahadi* negotiations. Because of the absence of *bohadi* negotiations, elderly people or parents do not feel as though they are morally obligated to assist in maintaining marriage, the foundation of which despised culture. These are legal titles, which are bestowed through *bohadi* negotiations and moral commitment that comes with marriage. The non-negotiated marriage will always lack moral support when young couples needs it most.

The significance of procreation in a negotiated marriage legitimises children as belonging to their father. Under normal circumstances, every child should take his or her father's surname; this further implies that in situations wherein the father's family performs a cultural ritual, this child will be part of it. However, in a case of a non-negotiated marriage, a child born out of such a union cannot be given his father's surname or participate rightfully in any ritual that takes place in the father's family. In other words, the father does not have a claim to his own children because there was no negotiation of *bohadi*. This aspect of legitimacy of the children born of the negotiated marriage through *mahadi* is further emphasised by Kirwen (2005: 116) who posits that failing to negotiate *mahadi* makes children illegitimate [...]. Mbiti agrees and argues that failing to negotiate *ilobolo/bohadi* is 'stealing' someone's daughter and making her a wife. Mbiti (1990: 140) elucidates:

The custom of presenting a gift to the bride's people [...] is an important institution in African societies. It is a token of gratitude on the part of the bridegroom's people to those of the bride, [...] and for allowing her to become his wife [...]. At marriage, she is not stolen but is given [...] under mutual agreement between the two families.

In the above citation Mbiti brings in the significance of *bohadi* negotiations or agreements, further emphasising the fact that the woman is not stolen. This has implications for *vat-en-sit* or non-negotiated unions. In reality, a man who did not negotiate *bohadi* does not even have the right to name his own children, let alone give them his family name. The good practice of *bohadi* negotiations is no longer what it used to be in 'the golden years'. Invasion of culture and cultural practices such as *mahadi* negotiate is unfortunate to the extent that negative meanings accompany these practices. One of the most important aspect of *mahadi* among some African groups is not limited to *mahadi* itself, it is extended to the exchange of gifts. As a principle both families exchange gifts, culturally, these gifts were inexpensive but a large number of people from both families were included to receive these gifts, these included deceased family members especially the father and the mother from both families. The symbolic meaning is that parents would forever be acknowledged and appreciated for the gift they left for the newly wedded. Furthermore, the exchange of gifts sealed the alliance

between these two families and established a permanent in-law relationship (Kirwen, 2005: 116).

THE VALUE OF LANGUAGE

There is abundance of literature about the value of language in philosophy and epistemology. This then makes one ask the question: what is language? Eleojo (2014: 363) discusses certain philosophers who wrote on the importance of language in philosophy, pointing out that philosophy is a discipline grounded on 'conceptual clarifications and analysis.' Different philosophers define language differently: for instance, for Malinowski (Finnegan, 2007: 2), language is a 'mode of action and not as an instrument of reflection,' while in the same source Austin defines language as 'performative utterances.' Finnegan (2007: 3) correctly understands language as 'verbalised action.' All Basotho idiomatic expressions directs action and thought. Accordingly, Masolo (2010: 37-44) articulates:

It is reasonable enough to expect every community to have its own language through which it adequately expresses and transmits its values to its members [...]. From an epistemological point of view, the importance of vernacular cannot be emphasized enough. Although it seems rather obvious that the language of any community reflects the structure of its world – that is, how the community understands, defines, and taxonomizes ideas about itself and its relations [...].

Wiredu (2007: 77) argues for philosophy and authenticity. Authenticity in our view rests on a number of things including one's connection with one's culture. Compromising and despising one's culture is a sign of weakness from those critiques. Basotho people have deep respect for their cultural practices. A woman, whose authenticity is appreciated through *bohadi* negotiations, will always carry pride with her, whereas the contrary is true about a Mosotho woman for whom there were no *bohadi* negotiations. For males, respect for culture can be internalised, and make a person a responsible moral agent and authentic cultural person.

Culture and language are interdependent and language is not politically neutral or value free. In the light of this, we can certainly suggest that distorting certain aspects of language compromises and undermines people's culture. As Metzger (1992: 23) puts it: 'In the process of [...] discovering our story, we restore those parts of ourselves that have been scattered, hidden, denied, distorted, forbidden and we come to understand that stories heal.' Indeed stories do heal but only if the stories relate people's voices and understood from the insiders' perspective.

Culturally, negotiating marriage is the most responsible way through which young people enter into marriage. For Africans, possession of cattle is a sign of wealth. Even in a case of hard cash, it is still *mahadi*. The language of paying *mahadi* which is problematic.

THE EPISTEMOLOGICAL OF MARRIAGE

Knowledge of being human, being a man or husband or being a woman or wife, is as important as one's existence. From a young age boys and girls are socialised epistemologically (i.e. how to be good husbands, wives and mothers). This knowledge they must carry through their whole lives. Although Basotho people did not know any formal education before the advent of missionaries in Lesotho, this does not mean that they did not educate young women and young men. At a certain age when young people were at the appropriate age, they had to go through initiation in the circumcision school called *mophato/lebollo*. The main purpose of going to *mophato* is to prepare young men and women for life ahead of them as husbands and wives, and thereafter as fathers and mothers. Matséla (1990: 25) summarises the purpose of *mophato* as a prerequisite to admission into marriage. *Mophato* initiated and prepared young men and women for adulthood and in particular marriage. Magesa (1998: 110) concurs that the 'entire process of initiation' prepares them for marriage and procreation. The order is prioritized as follows: marriage begins with young people sharing their love and involving their elders who proceed to negotiate *mahadi* and then give their ancestors' blessing to procreate and produce children. The spiritual aspect of negotiated marriage through *mahadi* has a relationship to a belief in ancestors, who usually bless the marriage with children. In Malegapura Makgoba (1999: 1v55-156) Teffo writes:

In African societies marriage and fertility is a culturally shared value, which is closely related to security and is regarded as a vital force in society. A man is considered a man of some standing in the community, when he gets married. A woman's prestige in the community culminates in marriage.

Cultural marriage is differentiable from the *vat-en-sit* situation in which the institution of marriage is undermined. Giving *ilobolo/mahadi* among Basotho people is equivalent to the respect both a prospective husband and wife deserve. Among Basotho people, a married woman receives a new name, which symbolises and recognises the passage to womanhood. Guma (2001: 267) emphasises the significance of naming among Basotho people: the same significance applies in the case of a woman who has entered into marriage through negotiations. As of now, she is *Mma...*, which means 'the mother of [...]' Semenya (2014) argues that marriage among Basotho people is a transition from childhood to adulthood and further articulates that prior to marriage there are certain processes that should take place; *mahadi* negotiations is top of these. The term 'motherhood' is not in the restricted western sense. 'Motherhood', in this cultural context, means that the newly wed woman should behave like a mature woman. Motherhood among Basotho is a moral status.

With a newly married man, the same applies. He is now an adult and thus stop behaving childishly. He should also associate with married men, the group within which he now belongs. He must work and do everything in his power to provide for his family. By its very nature, marriage is a compromise, into which two

people from completely different backgrounds agree to enter, thus necessitating this serious compromise.

Generally, marriage is about respecting the culture(s) of both persons who intend to marry, in particular the woman's cultural beliefs. Accordingly, Ogugua (2004: 60) notes: 'Culture basically unites humanity and divides humanity.' Subsequently, focussing on the two families and their extended relatives, recognition of the woman's culture can unite families and their extended members but it can seriously divide them. Hence, our argument that the main purpose of negotiating *mahadi* is to create a relationship and unite families; the contrary is also true where these negotiations do not take place.

There are common elements among a number of African cultural practices and one of those relates to the number of cattle requested as part of *mahadi*. It is therefore unwise to assume that the practice of *ukulobola* follows the same principles among Bantu speaking groups. Depending on the status of a young woman and her preservation of her virginity, eleven cattle (among AmaZulu) is normally a requirement: people would usually ask for between ten to twelve cattle for a virgin but not more. Among Basotho communities, fifteen cattle is a requirement. For a deflowered woman the number of cattle decreases. Generally, eleven cattle a 'normal' number for non-royal maidens, while for royal daughters the number increases. The term 'normal' means 'ordinarily' what the requirements are, but *monyala ka pedi* principle is an exception to the rule. The symbolic aspect is prioritise. Negotiating *mahadi* is among Africans fulfilling a legal requirement (Semenya, 2014). Failing to negotiate *mahadi* is failing to fulfil the legal aspect of marriage. The meaning of 'legal' does not mean the same as the western usage of 'legal' as in a 'civil marriage.' Once a woman's family receives a portion of *mahadi* this constitutes a marriage in an African sense.

Besides the legal aspects, *mahadi* serves both cultural and psychological existential needs of an African. The psychological purpose serves to make the newly wedded woman feel accepted and appreciated by her new family. This psychological aspect also ensures a woman's new place in the hierarchy of the family. *Mahadi* negotiation gives her approval, strength and status. Manyeli (1995: 264) argues that culture gives morality its form and significance. It is our understanding that cultures differ in many respects including in the requirements in negotiating marriage among Bantu speaking groups. However, even in cultures, where *mahadi* is not part of the negotiations, there are processes, which are in place and these outline the moral significance of negotiating marriage. We argue that negotiating marriage with the woman's parents is not only a sign of respect for the family and culture but also a moral obligation.

The moral epistemology plays an important role among Africans. This moral epistemology distinguishes right from wrong, and good from evil. As a moral principle, negotiating *bohadi* is regarded as good and right whereas *vat-en-sit* or failing to negotiate *bohadi* is rejected as wrong (Koenane, 2014: 2203). *Vat-en-sit* is an easy way out which compromises culture. Among Basotho people, it is a

legitimate expectation for parents to negotiate *mahadi* for their daughters, even when it means negotiating under the principle of *monyala ka pedi*.

To emphasise the relationship between the cultural and economic significance, Murray (1981: 146) elucidates:

It is impossible to isolate the material and 'economic' aspect of *bohadi* transfers from their ideological or 'cultural' aspect, and to ascribe priority to one or the other. *Bohadi* is 'cultural' in that Basotho affect resolutions of personal identity with reference to the transactions [...]. *Bohadi* is also 'economic' in that transfers in livestock and cash are substantial items of income and expenditure in household budget.

Three aspects for understanding *bohadi* are 'cultural', religious and 'economic' respectively. The cultural aspect is when *mahadi* are in the form of livestock. To avoid the controversy of commercialising *mahadi*, some families insist on the cultural aspect by negotiating *mahadi* in the form of livestock but this is usually the case only in rural areas. Another aspect of the cultural understanding is the symbolic value of the *monyala ka pedi*. The economic aspect is the most controversial for those who are not prepared to take into account the symbolic aspect of a cultural *bohadi* negotiation, which is usually the case in urbanised areas. The controversy arises when people literally ignore the symbolic meaning of *lobola* and asks for financial value – which amounts to hundreds of thousands of ZAR (South African currency) in monetary terms.

LINGUISTIC PROBLEMS OF MAHADI / ILOBOLO

Undeniably, there are problems related to *mahadi*. Firstly, young people no longer understand and appreciate certain or most cultural practices within their own backgrounds. Perhaps this is because of the commercialised world in which people find themselves. However, language, specifically, has a strong influence on our attitudes: if we use language with negative connotations, the effects on the mind will also be negative. There is nothing positive about the idea of 'bride price'. The word 'price' denotes value, amount or worth and it is in reference to buying or paying for material goods, whereas *mahadi* has completely different connotations. This endorses morality through *ubuntu* way of life, which does not put a price on human beings.

Language plays an important role in shaping lives and in directing lifestyles. Obiechina (1975: 156) writes:

Proverbs are [...] philosophical and moral expositions shrunk to a few words, and they form a mnemonic device in societies in which everything worth knowing and relevant to everyday life has to be committed to memory.

Proverbs among Basotho people are sources of wisdom. They are mechanisms, which convey moral lessons. To benefit from this wisdom, one needs to be thoroughly familiar with proverbs. The epistemic character of proverbs and idioms among Basotho people resides in their general applicability. Knowledge

and wisdom among Basotho people is impossible to measure just by acquisition of formal education. This supports Matséla's (1990) assertion that *mophato* is a traditional indigenous Basotho school where no one fails.

CONCLUSION

This article has examined Basotho marriage, focusing on the principle of *monyala ka pedi* as the basis for *mahadi* negotiations. We argued that in terms of this principle, people in impoverished circumstances are still able to get married despite their lack of money and possessions. We further discussed the 'cultural' and 'economic' aspects of *mahadi* negotiations were further discussed and it was stated that even in cases where agreements of *mahadi* negotiations are given in monetary form, they are still understood as *mahadi* cattle. The article has further discussed the controversy that characterises *mahadi* nowadays, relating to interpretations that *mahadi* equates to the commercialisation of women and thus disadvantages and devalues them. It has further been explained that *bohadi* among Africans in southern Africa constitutes marriage, notwithstanding the number of cattle given to the woman's family. However, we also argued that the interference of colonial powers, and missionaries in particular, changed the meaning of *mahadi* and discouraged it. We articulated that the meaning and significance attached to *mahadi* has changed because of cultural and linguistic misunderstanding. In contemporary times, the wrong use of language as seen in the expression 'paying' *mahadi/ilobolo* is normalised. Reducing this premarital tradition to a monetary exchange has fundamentally distorted the spirit and purpose of the original principle. This is to the detriment of young men when they wish to marry but do not have the financial resources to meet the demands of the young woman's family; and, equally undesirably, it degrades women by commodifying them and equating them with mere chattels. This new reality of what was previously an acceptable and noble act is nowadays distorted, hence the need to renegotiate the meaning of *mahadi* negotiation.

The article's purpose was to renegotiate and correct the wrong meaning attached to *mahadi* by young people and outsiders who completely miss the true spirit and purpose of *bohadi* negotiations. However, *bohadi* negotiation can divide people just as much as it has the capacity to unite them. Further, we argued that in as much as there are pitfalls in understanding the value of *mahadi* negotiation, there is also great value attached to it so long as we preserve its true cultural meaning and practise it without prejudice. We further argued that internalising cultural values has positive effects for young people. Moreover, *mahadi* negotiation as one aspect of the cultural heritage of Basotho people embraces the moral epistemology of differentiating between right and wrong. This led to the argument that negotiating and giving *mahadi* is the morally right thing to do. Failing and refusing to negotiate *mahadi* is morally wrong.

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